

METHODS OF FORMING THE SKILLS OF USING WRITTEN WEAPONS IN PUPILS OF THE 1ST CLASS

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Annotation: In recent decades, both educational theorists and practitioners have been paying more and more attention to the problems of developmental learning. Serious scientific works are devoted to this issue. Special programs, textbooks, and manuals are published to help teachers. Modern primary school, based on the principle of developmental learning, is in search of a model for the overall development of the child.

Keywords: graphic skills, school learning to write, calligraphic writing.

One of the sides of the General development of primary school children is the development of speech. Speech in General, as well as written speech, is a multi-faceted phenomenon. An important component of it is considered to be writing as the ability to use graphic signs to express the content of speech and thoughts of a person. Writing skills, and therefore graphic skills, are one of the most important aspects of a child's overall development.

As teachers and researchers point out, "writing is a higher quality of personality than even the most perfect calligraphy."

The development of writing can not be successful without mastering the writing technique itself, without mastering the graphic skill. We find confirmation of this in the works of many scientists.

K. D. Ushinsky, who made a significant contribution to the primary education system, was one of the first to speak about the conscious attitude to writing of primary school students. Ushinsky's didactic provisions, which defined the educational process in the primary classes of the people's school, established certain norms in teaching writing. His system combines the teaching of reading and writing was a turning point in the development of school learning to write. This led to the fact that learning the graphical representation letters becomes meaningful. He also emphasized the need to learn non-stop writing.

For the purpose of sequencing the learning of the letters 'outlines," writes V. A. Saglin, " each letter is decomposed into its constituent elements. First of all, children are trained in writing these elements, and then in writing the letter itself." In the first two years of children's education at school, it is necessary to pay great attention to the

element-by-element drawing of letters. It is only in the third grade that learning to write is faced with the task of developing cursive writing (speed and coherence of writing).

Methods: In the case of element-by-element drawing of letter signs, from the very beginning of learning to write, there was a gap between the visual and motor links in the formation of graphic writing skills. The visual component, on the one hand, acted as a passive factor. On the other hand, the method of detached writing during literacy training delayed the development of coherence and smooth hand movements of the writer at the subsequent stages of the formation of graphic writing skills.

Of course, the principle of piecemeal study of letters had a progressive meaning, since to a certain extent it contributed to the meaningful assimilation of letter signs by pupils. However, the transfer of visual elements of letters to the motor part of the writing process, performed mechanically, as well as repeated, unconscious reproduction of their children on paper, delayed the development of the technical, motor side of the writing skill.

Subject of research: formation of graphic skills and calligraphic writing and their impact on the overall development of students.

The hypothesis of the study: It can be assumed that the formation of graphic skills and calligraphic writing will be more successful and will contribute to the overall development of pupils if, taking into account the psycho physiological characteristics of primary school age and creating a favorable psychological climate in the learning process, the methods of teaching this type of activity will be based on the following pedagogical foundations:

- Using a new technology for developing graphic skills and calligraphic writing, which includes a writing algorithm developed in the course of the research –writing with open rules";
- The use of the writing algorithm creates conditions for the overall development of the child (development of intelligence, speech, reading speed, etc.);
- the process of children's emotional experience of success in learning will lead to the conscious acquisition of skills necessary to create positive motivation in learning to read and write.

We also assumed that a complete system of forming graphic skills and calligraphic writing will have a significant impact on the formation of correct graphic skills and improving writing literacy when correcting handwriting. The purpose, object, subject, and hypothesis of the study determined the following tasks:

1. To reveal the features of formation of graphic skills and calligraphic writing in psychological and pedagogical research and school practice.

2. Develop the technology and substantiate the content aspect of the pedagogical foundations that promote effective teaching of graphic skills and calligraphy in unity with the overall development of students.

3. Determine the content aspect of the writing algorithm that contributes to correcting the handwriting of students in grades 1-7.

4. Develop guidelines for the formation of graphic skills, calligraphy and handwriting correction

Results: The article reveals the pedagogical bases that take into account psycho-physiological features and are aimed at creating a favorable psychological climate, and the system of effective formation of graphic skills, calligraphic writing and handwriting correction based on them:

- A new technology for forming graphic skills has been created, which includes a writing algorithm developed during the research- «writing with open rules»;

- The main detailed elements of letters and ways of their connection, forming the basis of writing most letters of the Uzbek alphabet, are defined; specific private algorithms for writing each sign are disclosed;

- identified complex of methodical techniques of training based on developed through the study of didactic games; the inclusion of children in a situation in which the withdrawal often results from the psychological barrier of fear of time-consuming activity of writing (game, fabulous situation, journey);

- on the creation of a teacher "the situation of success" and psychological comfort;
- developed a system of handwriting correction for students of grades 1, as well as students of pedagogical Universities in Uzbekistan, colleges based on "ready-made knowledge of the main algorithm, search situations, experience of creative activity, emotional value relationships, a number of developed exercises that contribute to the extinction of the old skill and the predominance of the new, based on «writing with open rules". This research reveals some new approaches to the problem of writing formation in students. Timely and correctly formed graphic skill is the basis for further successful teaching of schoolchildren. Mastering the correct graphic skill significantly affects the development of students' native language and their overall development. Graphic skills and calligraphic writing are not an independent part of writing. Mastering writing, writing letters, signs, merging them into words serves to convey the semantic side of speech, the transfer of thought.

Many scientists-psychologists, didactics, and Methodists-have studied the psychological features and pedagogical foundations of graphic skills and calligraphic writing. The publications we analyzed reveal the psycho-physiological features of the primary acquisition of a child's graphic skill, the reasons for difficulties in mastering the skill-which are hidden in the child itself, in its age-related features - in the weak development of small hand muscles, in difficulties in coordinating visual and motor

images required for the graphic representation of letters, as well as in the imperfection of the writing system, in the imperfection of the methods of teaching recommended to the teacher and used by the teacher. Conclusion: The analysis of the history of the development of writing training shows that to date, scientists have recommended many methods and methods of teaching writing to school practice that are adequate to the task of forming the correct spelling of letters, speed of writing, and calligraphic handwriting. The tools of writing that correspond to the conditions of modern life, the nature of notebook layout, simplification of capital letters that contribute to smoothness, continuity, and, consequently, speed of writing are established. It is determined in what ratio the study of letters should be for mastering reading and writing; the main elements that make up the writing of the letters of the Uzbek alphabet are identified, and appropriate methodological techniques for teaching writing letters, their elements, and others are found. However, quite close attention to the problem of teaching writing by psychologists, teachers, and methodologists is not yet combined with sufficiently high results in mastering the technique of writing, its calligraphy, and mass school students. We can assume that this is to some extent due to the fact that the existing pedagogical and methodological literature has not yet developed a complete system of teaching writing. The research has shown that the method we developed for step-by-step formation of graphic skills and calligraphic writing is effective. In addition, the effectiveness of this work is largely determined by the high level of training of primary school teachers to teach children to write. In this regard, the teachers were offered a Copy book, a calligraphy Notebook, and a teacher's manual developed for first-grade pupils.

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